

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING ORIENTATION ON MANUFACTURING INDUSTRIES BUSINESS PERFORMANCE; THE ROLE OF ECO-INNOVATION AND SUSTAINABLE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN CHINA

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the parallel mediation of eco-innovation and sustainable competitive advantage in the relationship between green marketing orientation and business performance in manufacturing firms located in China. The positivist paradigm is adopted in this study, with 420 valid questionnaires collected from the managers and executives of manufacturing firms. The Smart-PLS has been used to analyze the data. Results show that three dimensions of green marketing orientation significantly impacts eco-innovation, sustainable competitive advantages, and business performance. Furthermore, it is also found that eco-innovation and sustainable competitive advantages mediate the relationship between green market orientation and business performance. The results also reveal the mediation of sustainable competitive advantages in the relationship between eco-innovation and business performance. This study has presented valuable insights for managers, owners, and executives of manufacturing firms and policymakers to gain sustainable business performance. This study provides a unique and original contribution to the existing body of knowledge on green marketing. It achieves this by combining insights from green marketing orientation, eco-innovation, and sustainable competitive advantage. The information it offers is highly helpful for managers and legislators, highlighting the importance of adopting a well-rounded approach to economic, environmental, and social concerns inside manufacturing companies. The novelty lies in showcasing how the implementation of a green market orientation and eco-innovation contributes to achieving a sustainable competitive advantage, consequently improving the overall performance of the organization. The study specifically examines the complex connection between these factors within manufacturing companies, providing novel viewpoints in the age of sustainable development and increased environmental consciousness.

Keywords: Eco-innovation; Sustainable Competitive Advantage; Green Marketing Orientation; Business Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global concern for environmental sustainability has compelled corporations to undergo a green transformation in their primary operations (Mady, Abdul Halim, & Omar, 2022). The manufacturing business has a significant environmental impact, characterized by its escalating worldwide resource utilization and release of pollutants (Rivera & Clement, 2019). The environment has become increasingly polluted despite the booming economy due to industrial output (Han et al., 2020). Pollution prevention, green manufacturing, waste reduction, recycling, and management, and resource consumption reduction are among the environmental concerns that manufacturing businesses must address (Saleem, Zhang-Zhang, Gopinath, & Malik, 2021). Consequently, there is mounting demand on manufacturing enterprises to embrace environmentally sustainable practices.

Sustainable practices and environmental concerns must also be considered in businesses' short-term and long-term planning; as environmental consciousness is a competitive differentiator in every market. Numerous academics have written on "green marketing" because of its relevance to sustainable practices and environmental concerns (García-Salirrosas & Rondon-Eusebio, 2022; Gbadeyan & Omolekan, 2015; Iqbal, Kazmi, Anwar, Ramish, & Salam, 2023; Sharma, 2021). As awareness of the need for environmental protection grows, more shoppers consider environmental impacts while purchasing. Furthermore, traditional marketing practices have been criticized for emphasizing consumer satisfaction over environmental protection (Ajike, Amos, & Kabuoh, 2015). The company's strategy in sustaining corporate sustainability through green innovation has also been inspired by green marketing (J. Chen & Liu, 2018). Eco-innovation is a strategic approach pursued by companies to achieve long-term breakthroughs while maintaining a competitive advantage and promoting environmental sustainability, according to some scholars (Nuryakin & Maryati, 2022; Soewarno, Tjahjadi, & Fithrianti, 2019). It is thus seen as the development of a novel business model, products, processes, managerial practices, corporate structures, and marketing strategies that meet the target of reducing environmental impacts (Maçaneiro, da Cunha, & Balbinot, 2013).

The threat of environmental degradation in China has prompted many companies to adopt environmental management systems and eco-innovation approaches (Zhang, Xue, & Zhou, 2019). There has been much focus on eco-innovation and sustainable competitive advantage to ensure a company's long-term environmental viability (Nuryakin & Maryati, 2022), and this trend has coincided with the onset of significant environmental deterioration. This study intends to provide some context on the green marketing orientation in China. China's rapid economic development has primarily been supported by the growth of its manufacturing sector, which makes low-priced but resource-intensive exports to other countries (Liu et al., 2012). The country's business sector largely causes pollution emissions in China. Chinese authorities have recently instituted stringent legislative measures mandating business investments in pollution prevention, environmentally friendly manufacturing processes, and general environmental protection

(Kong, Feng, Zhou, & Xue, 2016). As a result, Chinese companies worry that the cost of doing business will rise if they do not comply with considerably tighter environmental rules (Xia, Zhang, Yu, & Tu, 2019). However, this may not be the best way to ensure long-term success in protecting the environment. The long-term success needs green innovation, which not only increases business profits but also provides a sustainable competitive advantage (F. Shaukat, Zaman, Nguyen, & Souvanhxay, 2023). This study investigates the impact of green marketing orientation on business performance through the mediating roles of sustainable competitive advantage and eco-innovation among the Chinese manufacturing industry. With this knowledge, we may implement systems that encourage eco-innovation and other "green" marketing strategies that provide a lasting competitive advantage.

Our study makes three important contributions. First, we integrate green marketing orientation theory, natural resource-based theory (S. L. Hart & Dowell, 2011), sustainable competitive advantage, and eco-innovation to study corporate environmental strategies (Latan, Jabbour, de Sousa Jabbour, Wamba, & Shahbaz, 2018). Second, our study contributes to knowledge of Chinese manufacturing enterprises' green strategies. We demonstrate that competitive strategies boost eco-innovation's business performance impact. This outcome expands earlier research because our study was undertaken in a situation not extensively represented in corporate green marketing literature. Our study focuses on emerging countries, unlike past research that focused on Western nations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Green Marketing Orientation

According to Kotler et al. (2009), green marketing can be described as the practice of fulfilling the present needs of consumers and businesses, while simultaneously safeguarding and improving the capacity and responsibility of future generations to meet their own needs (Armstrong & Kotler, 2009). Lazer (1969) emphasizes that green marketing goes beyond simply examining the ecological effects of marketing. It also amplifies the urgency to actively address environmental concerns within marketing strategies and practice. By increasing marketing efficiency and decreasing marketing expenditures, businesses were able to increase profits thanks to green marketing methods. They also found that companies that practice sustainability tend to have more favorable management and advertising outcomes. There is a positive correlation between green products, green personnel, green promotion, green distribution, green price, green technique, and green physical proof and the success of an enterprise (BM Eneizan, K Abd Wahab, & TF Obaid, 2016). A company's image and bottom line can both benefit from green marketing (Mukonza & Swarts, 2020). The importance of green marketing is underscored by the rise of new green industries globally (Kautish & Sharma, 2020). Marketers are recognizing the significance of addressing environmental concerns and promoting sustainability. This highlights a collective commitment to a greener future through effective marketing strategies.

Green market orientation (GMO) disseminates green values and norms throughout an organization's strategy and operations. The competitive environment begins with changes in product design, examines enterprise culture, and concludes with an examination of environmental impact analysis in the sequence of eco-competitive beneficial advantages (Moravcikova, Krizanova, Kliestikova, & Rypakova, 2017). According to Papadas 2018, green marketing orientation consists of three dimensions: strategic green marketing orientation, tactical green marketing orientation, and internal green marketing orientation. Its working definitions are as follows: (1) Strategic green marketing is the degree to which businesses incorporate the orientation environmental imperative into strategic marketing decisions; (2) Tactical green marketing is the degree to which businesses actualize orientation environmental values in tactical marketing decisions; (3) Internal green marketing is the degree to which all internal stakeholders adopt the corporate environmental orientation's values (Papadas, Avlonitis, & Carrigan, 2017). Integration of green values into business strategy (Banerjee, Bhattacharjee, & Kommareddy, 2002) and stakeholder integration for economic, social, and environmental performance (Simão & Lisboa, 2017) are examples of strategic green marketing orientation (SGM). (2) Tactical green marketing orientation (TGM) entails short-term measures that turn the conventional marketing mix into a greener one (Pujari, Wright, & Peattie, 2003), promotion tools (Kilbourne, Beckmann, & Thelen, 2002), supply chain actions (Zhu & Sarkis, 2004), and pricing policies (C. Chen, 2001) via online communication to attract new and strategic audiences (Kotler, 2011). Lastly, (3) internal green marketing orientation (IGM) refers to a company's internal culture with green principles that are used to help the company and its personnel (via training, awareness efforts, etc.) in marketing its purpose to customers (Wells, Manika, Gregory-Smith, Taheri, & McCowlen, 2015).

The Business Performance:

Businesses are adapting to the changing landscape by adopting environmentally sustainable practices and complying with environmental laws, aiming to improve their performance (Leonidou, Katsikeas, & Morgan, 2013). There is growing importance for incorporating green practices for businesses to thrive in a sustainable manner. According to the research conducted by Emeizan et al. (2016), the implementation of a green marketing strategy has a significant positive impact on increasing sales volume for green cars. Additionally, green marketing strategies contribute to the improvement of total quality management and provide new business opportunities, markets, segments of consumers, and unique product positioning (Y.-S. Chen, 2010). Furthermore, other studies have established a positive relationship between environmental green practices in the service industry and overall performance (BM Eneizan, K Abd Wahab, & TF Obaid, 2016; Wanjohi, Gachoka, Kihoro, & Ogutu, 2013). Based on these findings, the study proposed the following hypothesis.

H1: Green marketing orientation is positively related to business performance.

Green Marketing Orientation and Eco-Innovation

The greening of different components of traditional marketing is discussed (Kotler et al., 2008) in social marketing and discussions of limited environmental resources and conventional marketing. According to a study (Martínez, 2015), "green marketing" is "marketing that serves the demands of consumers and businesses today while conserving or enhancing the ability and caring for future generations to meet their needs." Consideration of marketing's effect on people and the planet is the first step in green marketing. Furthermore, green marketing raises awareness of the environmental impact of marketing and the importance of addressing environmental concerns in the marketing sector (Kotler et al., 2008). The idea of a "green marketing orientation" was created due to this research. A sustainable competitive advantage (Cao, Ajjan, Hong, & Logistics, 2018) is what a company aims for with its green marketing focus. Recent years have seen a rise in the literature concerning green marketing, environmental sustainability, and commercial ethics (Papadas, Avlonitis, Carrigan, & Piha, 2019). However, consumer orientation is a popularly studied market orientation idea from the 1990s. (Kohli & Jaworski, 1990) argue that a market-oriented perspective is essential for a company to achieve the performance typified by steady growth and the creation of innovations. In addition, researchers (Slater & Narver, 1995) proposed a correlation between market orientation and innovation outcomes, namely the success rate of new product innovations. According to scholars (Carbonell & Escudero, 2010), organizations must react quickly to shifts in client demand to keep up with their more competitive rivals. According to research (AlQershi, Mokhtar, & Abas, 2020), organizational competence significantly affects the rate of innovation, leading to better results when developing new products. The notion of eco-innovation-oriented green marketing was established and evaluated in this study. The green product innovation is crucial to the success of businesses in the realms of collaborative innovation (C. H. Chang & Chen, 2013), and green organizational identity (Lin, Tan, & Geng, 2013), and enhancing the efficiency of the industrial sector (Ar, 2012). For businesses to thrive, (Cronin, Smith, Gleim, Ramirez, & Martinez, 2011) stressed the need for ongoing development of environmentally friendly policies and creating a path to address the interests of a wide range of stakeholders by creating and developing environmentally friendly products. Eco-innovation, green processes, and green alliances were identified as the three main types of green strategies in the literature. Eco-innovation, our initial tactic, focuses on new and improved eco-friendly goods. An approach to developing greener products and methods of doing business. Researchers dug deeper and discovered that internal green capabilities, R&D intensity, and firm size all played a role in whether or not a company adopted an eco-innovation product or service. Therefore, businesses should establish a green marketing strategy to differentiate their products from the competition and increase sales (Dabija, Bejan, & Grant, 2018). Numerous academic investigations have concluded that an eco-innovation marketing focus is a vital strategic option for businesses seeking to differentiate their offerings in the marketplace (Chatzoglou & Chatzoudes, 2017; Enzing, Batterink, Janszen, & Omta, 2011; S. Shaukat, Nawaz, & Naz, 2013). Companies embrace green product innovation and green process innovation as strategies to fulfill the

demands of environmentally conscious consumers and reduce the unfavorable effects of manufacturing processes on the environment. Hence, organizations must embrace green innovation to effectively respond to demands from customers, competitors, and regulatory authorities. The company gains a competitive advantage over its rivals' products in negotiations with clients due to the distinct product values and environmental advantages of its eco-friendly items. Thus, the researcher developed the initial hypothesis.

H2: Green marketing orientation (GMO) is positively related to eco-innovation.

Eco-Innovation and Business Performance

The company's eco-innovation is key to successful green marketing efforts (Aprisma & Sudaryati, 2020). Green innovation encompasses product and process advancements that involve energy efficiency, pollution mitigation, waste reduction, and the creation of eco-friendly product designs. The company's commitment to cultivating an innovative environment places a greater emphasis on marketing activities aimed at influencing the development and success of products. (Lertpachin, Wingwon, & Noithonglek, 2013). Businesses need to create designs for their innovations that are flexible enough to meet the needs of their target audiences. Because of this, their products are well-received in the market (Fernández-Mesa, Alegre-Vidal, Chiva-Gómez, & Gutiérrez-Gracia, 2013), and the business has adopted environmentally responsible policies (Meirun, Makhloufi, & Ghozali Hassan, 2020). According to Soewarno et al. (2019) (Soewarno, Tjahjadi, & Permatanadia, 2020), an eco-innovation approach can increase an organization's environmental consciousness and its level of performance. Green innovation, encompassing environmentally friendly product development and process improvements, is crucial for companies to generate higher profits, while green process innovation directly affects organizational and environmental performance. Embracing green innovation presents strategic opportunities for companies, highlighting the positive correlation between superior green innovation and business success. Based on these arguments, hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Eco-innovation is positively related to business performance.

The implementation of stricter environmental regulations has transformed consumer behavior, leading to heightened environmental consciousness and a preference for eco-friendly products (Kumar & Ghodeswar, 2015). Consequently, companies are increasingly aligning their focus towards environmentally responsible markets, assuming greater social and environmental responsibilities (El-Kassar & Singh, 2019). Furthermore, the application of green technology is crucial to the long-term viability of a company (Suler, Palmer, & Bilan, 2021). In particular, it is simpler for businesses to achieve performance if they embrace the idea of eco-innovation in developing their products. For instance, (Enzing et al., 2011) discussed how product success was related to innovation. Several more studies provided additional context for the importance of innovation in assisting businesses in establishing themselves as market leaders in their product categories (Bakar & Ahmad, 2010; Salavou & Avlonitis, 2008). Based on this, hypothesis 4 is proposed:

H4: There exists a mediating role of Eco-innovation between Green Marketing Orientation and business performance.

Green Marketing Orientation and Sustainable Competitive Advantage

The idea of green marketing, which has been developing since the 1980s, is a variant of the traditional marketing model (Peattie & Crane, 2005).. When a company's stakeholders genuinely invest in protecting the environment, it benefits eco-innovation. To maintain its performance (Qi, Zou, & Xie, 2020), an organization must also pay close attention to marketing features that reflect its commitment to environmental protection and shape its standing in the eyes of its target audience. Previously a correlation between environmentally responsible actions and long-term sustainability was discovered in a study by (May, Hao, & Carter, 2021). The proactive environmental strategies provide companies with competitive advantages by enabling the utilization of rare, unique, and complex capabilities that aid in differentiation (O. Hart, 1995). It involves implementing strategic processes like researching and developing green products and establishing recycling systems. Following this line of thought, (Barney, 1991) defined sustained competitive advantage as consistently reaping benefits by implementing unique value-creation techniques in an industry where potential rivals cannot repeat these gains. The advantage in the market over rivals that can be maintained over time (Porter, 1989) is what we mean when we talk about a company having a sustainable competitive advantage. Among the business dynamics and growing competitive advantage (Wang, 2019), questions of business sustainability focused on environmentally friendly operational activities become a fascinating issue of research discussion. The RBV theory highlights the importance of leveraging green marketing as a valuable resource to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage in the marketplace. In the context of green marketing, adopting environmentally sustainable practices, developing eco-friendly products, and effectively communicating a commitment to sustainability can be viewed as valuable resources that differentiate a company from its competitors. This led them to suggest their alternative hypothesis.

H5: Green marketing orientation has positive relationship to sustainable competitive advantage.

Sustainable competitive advantage and business performance

In order to be more effective at following the principles and meeting environmental regulations, businesses need to make investments—organizations with better resource management impact how people in their communities' act. Managers' values and beliefs substantially influence whether or not their organizations care about environmental conditions and make decisions accordingly. Further, a sustainable competitive advantage might change as the market and competition evolve (Nandakumar, Ghobadian, & O'Regan, 2010). The operating cost efficiency and the creation of excellence are simplified for businesses that have adapted to their surroundings. The company's capacity to expand its market share is influenced by the consistency with which its product quality is maintained (Ledwith & O'Dwyer, 2008). The commercial viability of innovative

offerings has gained importance for many businesses and it leads towards competitive advantage. Market shifts, technological developments, and rivalry necessitate adaptation, and the innovative activities that help businesses do so, including developing environmentally friendly products, are encouraged (Simpson, 2004). Another study found that innovation was critical to helping businesses get a competitive edge and boost their advertising results (Mannan, Khurana, & Haleem, 2016). a company's green strategy can significantly assist in developing environmentally friendly new products. Sustainable innovation and environmental performance were given higher priority. They said businesses with an eye towards the future place a premium on long-term viability. This led them to the fourth hypothesis they tested.

H6: Sustainable competitive advantage is positively related to business performance.

H7: Sustainable competitive advantage mediates the relationship between green marketing orientation and business performance.

Eco-innovation and sustainable competitive advantage

The success of a company's product development is based on the degree to which it innovates, prioritizes its marketing efforts, and has a well-developed brand (Lertpachin et al., 2013). It is also discussed how a corporation that prioritizes and finances innovative activity would gain an advantage as the market becomes more open and full of rivalry dynamics. When gaining a sustainable competitive edge, eco-innovation is the way to go (Ar, 2012). Making management plans that consider environmental factors and the significance of accommodating consumer wants into account to maximize performance is also an integral part of environmental management (Sezen & Cankaya, 2013). Whether businesses may gain a competitive edge by focusing on environmental factors is still a topic of study for many academics (Jämsä, Tähtinen, Ryan, Pallari, & Development, 2011). Without investing in green product innovation, businesses cannot maintain a competitive edge or improve their products' performance over the long term. Companies can produce items that meet market potential by utilizing market resource allocation tactics to boost product distinctiveness and considering the potential for product creation for clients (Bradley & O'Reagain, 2001). According to research by (Nuryakin & Maryati, 2020), product innovation is crucial to a company's ability to gain a market advantage. Sustainable competitive advantage (CCA) creation, for instance, fosters eco-innovation to meet customer needs (Soebandrija, 2017). According to Chang's (2011) (N.-J. Chang & Fong, 2010) research, a company can get a competitive edge through the eco-innovation process by prioritizing environmental protection. In addition, particular works of literature and other empirical investigations have documented the connection between innovation and environmental issues (Lin et al., 2013), economic activity, and environmental sustainability (Lavrinenko, Ignatjeva, Ohotina, Rybalkin, & Lazdans, 2019). However, there is considerable debate in the academic literature over how green product innovation affects businesses' competitive advantage. Several studies have shown a positive correlation between eco-innovation and market advantage. For instance, Dangelico, Pujari, and Pontrandolfo (2017) (Dangelico, Pujari, & Pontrandolfo, 2017)

highlight the growing strategic importance of green product innovation among the world's leading manufacturers. Therefore, the authors came up with the hypotheses.

H8: Eco-innovation is positively related to sustainable competitive advantage.

H9: There exists a mediation effect of Sustainable competitive advantage between Eco-innovation and Business Performance.

It is important to note that this study considers several criteria before settling on China's manufacturing sector as its focus. The first principal component is China's manufacturing sector. After 40 years of tremendous development, China's manufacturing sector is now the largest in the world. It was nearly 30% of China's total economic output in 2028. However, manufacturing enterprises continue to face challenges, including product quality, a lack of world-famous brands, inefficient use of resources, and widespread environmental pollution. These flaws have severely hampered the progress of China's manufacturing sector, making a shift to a more sustainable development model necessary. As a second point, developing nations can learn from China by following some of the country's most crucial development patterns and pathways. As a result, Asian businesses will benefit from China's green development strategy for the industrial sector. Third, the phrase "made in China" is now one of the most widely known marks internationally. Any effort to improve the image of Chinese manufacturers abroad will have dramatic consequences for foreign firms wanting to do business with them.

3. METHODS

Sample and Procedure:

This study uses a survey method to test the research hypotheses. According to the research recommendations of (Churchill Jr, 1979), questionnaire items should be created in accordance with the following scientific processes: (A) The organization of variable elements should be based on the pertinent literature. (b) Back translation of measurement elements is required. The mature scale utilized in this research is offered in English and is primarily drawn from English-language literature. Chinese-to-English translation is done first, followed by the English translation, and the outcome is then compared to the source item. The procedure is as follows: two professors from Chinese universities who are fluent in English and my supervisor, who has experience in management and professional translation, back-translate the measurement items and continuously debate the confusing ones to create an initial Chinese scale. This study employs a 5-point Likert scale, with one denoting strongly disagree and five denoting strongly agree. To make the questionnaire easier to grasp, the phrasing and expression of the items were changed.

There were three sections to the questionnaire. The introduction, which primarily describes the context and goal of the questionnaire, is the first section. Descriptive information, such as the characteristics of Chinese manufacturing businesses (geographical location, category, size, age, and type of ownership), is included in the second section of the questionnaire (gender, age, education, experience, and job title). The third component is the evaluation of competitive advantage, green product

innovation, green emotional competence, and business reputation. The items and questionnaire components are displayed in Appendix A.

CEOs, CMOs, marketing managers, CSR managers, and department heads at Chinese manufacturing companies provided the information for this empirical study. Three sources were used for the data collection: First, the data from students of MBA executives working in the industry. Secondly, using Chinese apps, e.g., WeChat, for the electronic survey, and thirdly, got help from industry groups and committees to collect data. There are 950 paper surveys sent out, with a recovery rate of 48.3% based on the number of returned surveys (459). Only 420 questionnaires (63 on paper and 357 online) were considered complete after removing those with missing data, yielding a response rate of 44.2%. The respondents' demographics are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Respondents Demographics (N=420)

Dimension	N	%
Gender		
Male	307	73.1
Female	113	26.9
Age		
30-39	119	28.3
40-49	176	41.9
50-59	27	6.4
60-69	85	20.2
Above 70	13	3.1
Job Title		
Managers	58	13.8
Marketing Managers	178	42.4
CMO	23	5.5
Supervisors	18	4.3
CSR Manager	74	17.6
Others	69	16.4
Experience		
< 5 years	108	25.7
5-10	155	36.9
11-20	97	23.1
20-30	34	8.1
more than 30 Y	26	6.2
Education		
Bachelors	149	35.5
Masters	187	44.5
Others	84	20.0
Industries		
Auto industry	66	15.7
Solar	105	25
Chemical	57	13.5
Oil Firms	93	22.14
Pharmaceutical	29	6.9
Others	70	16.6

Measures

Following well established measurement scales were used to in the study based on 5 point Likert Scale.

Green Marketing Orientation: GMO was measured through 03 dimensions- strategic marketing orientation, tactical marketing orientation, and internal green marketing orientation - having the 21 item scale developed and validated by researchers (Papadas et al., 2017). Having, 9, 5, and 7 items, respectively. (Cronbach's alpha = 0.94).

Eco-Innovation: Eco-innovation was measured using the scale developed by Kusi (2015) (Kusi-Sarpong, Bai, Sarkis, & Wang, 2015). This scale consists of three items. (Cronbach's alpha = 0.68).

Sustainable Competitive Advantage: Eco-innovation was measured using the scale developed by Chang (2011) (C.-H. Chang, 2011). This scale consists of four items. (Cronbach's alpha = 0.794).

Business Performance Eco-innovation was measured using the scale developed by Barke (1984) (Burke, 1984). This scale consists of nine items. (Cronbach's alpha = 0.791).

4. RESULTS

Partial least squares SEM (PLS-SEM) version 3.2.8 was used to test the studied model. Internal consistency (reliability) of indicators, convergent validity, and discriminant validity are used to assess the validity and reliability of the measurement model. In this investigation, the CR for each construct is shown in Table 2 and is in the range of 0.8 and 0.9, above the recommended threshold value of 0.7. Results show that the used scales have adequate internal consistency. All item loadings and T-statistic values for each construct displayed in Table 2 showed adequate reliability. Referring Table 2, the AVE > .5 demonstrates that the measuring model used in the study has sufficient convergent validity.

Table 2: Items Loadings, Reliability and Convergent Validity

Construct	Item	Factor Loading	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Strategic green marketing orientation	SGMO1	0.906	0.943	0.946	0.690
	SGMO2	0.859			
	SGMO3	0.861			
	SGMO4	0.815			
	SGMO5	0.883			
	SGMO6	0.853			
	SGMO7	0.856			
	SGMO8	0.853			
	SGMO9	0.781			
Tactical green	TGMO1	0.897	0.805	0.807	0.563
	TGMO2	0.840			
	TGMO3	0.899			

marketing orientation	TGMO4	0.869			
	TGMO5	0.905			
Internal green marketing orientation	IGMO1	0.862	0.867	0.867	0.558
	IGMO2	0.880			
	IGMO3	0.897			
	IGMO4	0.840			
	IGMO5	0.091			
	IGMO6	0.862			
	IGMO7	0.880			
Sustainable competitive advantage	SCA1	0.907	0.794	0.804	0.618
	SCA2	0.883			
	SCA3	0.911			
	SCA4	0.850			
Eco-innovation	EI1	0.870	0.687	0.616	0.688
	EI2	0.894			
	EI3	0.881			
	EI4	0.855			
Business Performance	BP1	0.844	0.791	0.821	0.692
	BP2	0.873			
	BP3	0.840			
	BP4	0.852			
	BP5	0.875			
	BP6	0.859			
	BP7	0.869			
	BP8	0.829			
	BP9	0.862			

Discriminant Validity

Fornell and Larcker's criterion and cross-loading are used to evaluate the discriminant validity of the measurement model. A measurement model has discriminant validity if both (1) the correlations between the measure and all other measures are smaller than the square root of the AVE and (2) the indicator loadings are larger against their respective constructs than against other constructs.

For this reason, the Smart PLS algorithm's function of generating the AVE value of each construct is used to determine the initial assessment of the measurement model's discriminant validity.

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6
1: Business Performance	0.714					
2: Eco-Innovation	0.641	0.700				
3: Internal GM	0.391	0.504	0.747			
4: Strategic GM	0.413	0.482	0.689	0.831		
5: Sustainable Competitive Advantage	0.489	0.535	0.646	0.92	0.786	
6: Tactical GM	0.468	0.529	0.525	0.687	0.668	0.750

Referring Table 3, off-diagonal values are larger than the square roots of AVE demonstrated that Fornell and Larker's condition for discriminant validity is satisfied.

Table 4: Cross Loadings

	Business Performance	Eco-Innovation	Internal Green marketing orientation	Sustainable Competitive Advantage	Strategic green marketing orientation	Tactical green marketing orientation
BP1	0.595	0.505	0.137	0.354	0.258	0.263
BP2	0.706	0.496	0.300	0.344	0.269	0.330
BP3	0.651	0.492	0.303	0.387	0.309	0.394
BP4	0.671	0.332	0.184	0.277	0.141	0.216
BP5	0.059	-0.025	-0.013	-0.027	-0.173	-0.009
BP6	0.708	0.376	0.253	0.311	0.223	0.307
BP7	0.641	0.299	0.239	0.288	0.297	0.269
BP8	0.703	0.469	0.444	0.334	0.392	0.493
BP9	0.625	0.314	0.098	0.236	0.197	0.049
EI1	0.321	0.587	0.267	0.279	0.196	0.311
EI2	0.461	0.771	0.326	0.388	0.382	0.397
EI3	0.542	0.673	0.375	0.397	0.345	0.380
EI4	0.375	0.666	0.384	0.367	0.351	0.335
IGMO1	0.347	0.429	0.785	0.447	0.490	0.651
IGMO2	0.354	0.490	0.668	0.557	0.530	0.721
IGMO3	0.244	0.294	0.787	0.382	0.429	0.536
IGMO4	0.295	0.418	0.730	0.521	0.599	0.657
IGMO5	0.264	0.296	0.780	0.419	0.475	0.515
IGMO6	0.210	0.331	0.690	0.503	0.508	0.646
IGMO7	0.313	0.351	0.778	0.520	0.545	0.561
SCA1	0.248	0.343	0.494	0.716	0.600	0.525
SCA2	0.416	0.408	0.561	0.777	0.541	0.502
SCA3	0.359	0.452	0.484	0.833	0.718	0.521
SCA4	0.487	0.466	0.500	0.813	0.704	0.557
SGMO1	0.300	0.429	0.613	0.741	0.894	0.535
SGMO1	0.300	0.429	0.613	0.741	0.894	0.535
SGMO2	0.437	0.454	0.602	0.635	0.849	0.618
SGMO3	0.243	0.347	0.616	0.692	0.857	0.559
SGMO4	0.272	0.470	0.667	0.614	0.816	0.645
SGMO5	0.345	0.389	0.576	0.706	0.880	0.559
SGMO6	0.352	0.443	0.597	0.685	0.844	0.610
SGMO7	0.366	0.378	0.529	0.679	0.813	0.542
SGMO8	0.393	0.361	0.507	0.596	0.798	0.539
SGMO9	0.408	0.316	0.412	0.557	0.708	0.522
TGMO1	0.412	0.429	0.587	0.512	0.524	0.805
TGMO2	0.399	0.424	0.555	0.456	0.514	0.697
TGMO3	0.194	0.292	0.673	0.449	0.499	0.749
TGMO3	0.194	0.292	0.673	0.449	0.499	0.749
TGMO4	0.381	0.436	0.574	0.495	0.492	0.746
TGMO5	0.375	0.406	0.697	0.587	0.545	0.752

Analyzing the loadings of the indicators concerning all construct correlations is a second way to test discriminant validity. The Table 4 depicts the loading and cross-loading of items measuring each construct. The adequate loading of each item for the same construct and lower loading for other constructs indicate the discriminant and convergent validity of the measurement model. Keeping in view the findings of [73], the values as low as 0.052 for the SRMR indicate a well-fitting model for the observed trend. The table 5 shows heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) that is used to assess discriminant validity in structural equation modeling. The acceptable range for HTMT is between 0 and 1. The result in the table 5 falls in acceptable range.

Table 5: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

	EI	GMO	IGMO	SGMO	SCA	TGMO
EI	0.860					
GMO	0.517	0.714				
IGMO	0.449	0.682	0.783			
SGMO	0.480	0.620	0.767	0.754		
SCA	0.596	0.756	0.608	0.777	0.805	
TGMO	0.541	0.752	0.596	0.480	0.788	0.835

Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)

The outcomes of a structural model are put to use as predictive functions for the interrelationships between constructs. The PLS-SEM method then returns the R^2 value for the variance explained by these forecasts. The table shows that the R^2 values (Sarstedt, Ringle, Henseler, & Hair, 2014) for the model are greater than the minimum threshold of 0.10 (Falk & Miller, 1992), indicating that the model has adequate in-sample predictive power. Effect size of an explanatory (exogenous) variable can be calculated through f^2 . The green marketing orientation is measured through its dimensions SGMO, IGMO, and TGMO, whereas business performance is predicted by SCA and EI indirectly and directly through the green marketing orientation.

Table 6: R^2 and F^2 Values

Sr No	Variable	f^2	Variable	R^2
1	SGMO-->GMO	1.345	BP	0.838
2	TGMO-->GMO	2.345	EI	0.838
3	IGMO-->GMO	1.09	GMO	0.836
4	GMO-->SCA	1.438	IGMO	0.939
5	GMO-->EI	1.234	SCA	0.819
6	GMO-->BP	2.9	SGMO	0.944
7	SCA-->BP	2.83	TGMO	0.942
8	EI-->BP	1.492		

Keeping in view the foregone testing of measurement model, it can be concluded that model is fit for further analysis.

Structural Model Assessment

We used a systematic approach to testing each hypothesis. This study began by examining the direct effect of a green marketing strategy on bottom-line results. Phase two examined how focusing on green marketing directly affects long-term competitive advantage and eco-innovation. Next, we looked at how SCA and eco-innovation affect company results directly. The relevance of direct routes was determined using the Bootstrap resampling technique (Ringle, Wende, & Will, 2005) with 5,000 resamples. The results of the tests conducted on the hypothesis positing direct relationships and mediation results are shown in Tables 7.

Table 7: Results for studied path

Hypotheses	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	p
H ₁ : Green Marketing -> Business Performance	0.456	9.314	.000
H ₂ : Green Marketing -> Eco Innovation	0.552	11.189	.000
H ₃ : Eco Innovation -> Business Performance	0.562	13.697	.000
H ₅ : Green Marketing -> Sustainable Competitive Advantage	0.796	31.918	.000
H ₆ : Sustainable Competitive Advantage -> Business Performance	0.206	24.420	.006
H ₈ : Eco Innovation -> Sustainable Competitive Advantage	0.138	17.039	.002
Mediation Results:			
H ₄ : GMO ---> EI -> BP	0.295	7.333	.000
H ₇ : GMO --> SCA ---> BP	0.148	2.342	.009
H ₉ : EI ---> SCA ---> BP	0.028	1.944	.052

From Table 7, following results have been concluded:

H₁: The results reveal a substantial positive influence of green marketing orientation on business performance for the manufacturing industry of China ($\beta = 0.45$, $t = 9.314$, $p = 0.001$). Therefore, H₁ was supported.

H₂: The results reveal that there is a significant direct positive influence of green marketing orientation on eco-innovation ($\beta = 0.55$, $t = 11.189$, $p = 0.000$). Therefore, the hypothesis is supported.

H₃: The results reveal that there is a significant direct positive influence of eco-innovation on business performance for the manufacturing industry of China ($\beta = 0.56$, $t = 13.69$, $p = 0.001$). Therefore, H₃ is supported.

H₅: The results reveal a significant direct positive influence of green marketing orientation on sustainable competitive advantage ($\beta = 0.79$, $t = 31.918$, $p = 0.001$). Therefore, H₅ is supported.

H₆: The results reveal significant sustainable competitive advantage on business performance ($\beta = 0.20$, $t = 24.42$, $p = 0.003$). Hence, H₆ was rejected.

H₈: The results reveal a significant positive influence of eco-innovation on business performance ($\beta = 0.14$, $t = 17.03$, $p = 0.001$). Hence, H₈ was accepted in China in this study.

Mediation Analysis

H4: The results of a mediation analysis reveal that no mediation was found for eco-innovation on green marketing orientation and business ($\beta= 0.039, t= 0.732, p=0.464$). Hence, no mediation was found for the H4 hypothesis in this study.

H7: The results of a mediation analysis reveal that partial mediation was found for sustainable competitive advantage on green marketing orientation and business performance in this study ($\beta= 0.004, t= 0.107, p=0.915$). Hence, partial mediation was found for the H7 hypothesis in this study.

5. DISCUSSION

Eco-innovation is a more all-encompassing process than simply complying with environmental standards; therefore, first, manufacturers must take the initiative to execute it (Y. Zhou, Hong, Zhu, Yang, & Zhao, 2018). Not only do customer demands and product

lifespans dictate the need for eco-innovation, but so do social and environmental pressures and opportunities (Arfi, Hikkerova, & Sahut, 2018; S. S. Zhou, Zhou, Feng, Jiang, & Organization, 2019). The People's Republic of China's Ministry of Industry and Information Technology has just released a document predicting that by 2020, industrial enterprises larger than the designated size will use 18% less energy per unit of industrial value-added than they did in 2015 and that they will use 23% less water per unit of industrial value-added than they did in 2015. The total degree of green industrial growth will also increase significantly, and a system to promote green development will take shape. Therefore, manufacturing businesses should foster an eco-innovation mindset, incorporate the idea of green development into the design process, and make it clear that green product innovation is a process in which critical social groups collaborate. Several internal and external elements also play a role in this procedure.

Nevertheless, manufacturers need to discover or cultivate a willingness to pay for environmental quality, adhere to stringent environmental rules, and seek reliable data on the environmental qualities of their products. In order to mitigate threats and preserve or grasp opportunities to create value, manufacturing firms must design regulatory and market strategies in concert with one another. There are risks associated with implementing green product innovation that vary depending on the company and the industry or market in which it operates. Therefore, manufacturing businesses wishing to engage in eco-innovation based on their actual conditions should pick items that correspond with the scope of their own business. Companies can gain a sustainable competitive advantage by incorporating environmental protection into product design, production, packaging, sales, recycling, etc. This can be accomplished by exploring green product innovation paths appropriate for their development, which include continuously identifying differentiated product strategies, establishing or reshaping core competencies, acquiring unique technologies, amassing intellectual property rights, and so on (Mahdi & Almsafir, 2014).

Second, industrial producers need to prioritize building eco-innovation and green dynamic capabilities. An example of a dynamic capability that is hard to imitate by rivals is "green dynamic capability." A company's ability to dynamically align its resources (including its business models) with customer demands and expectations is measured by its "green dynamic capability" (Teece, 2018). Before creating an internal performance evaluation system based on learning outcomes, businesses must increase the learning motivation of their internal elites and cultivate a conducive learning environment. In order for businesses to effectively use, integrate, merge, produce, acquire, share, and transform new green technology, they must pay full attention to the environmental concerns of stakeholders and actively work with their key users, suppliers, and universities (De Marchi, 2012). In addition, businesses need efficient methods of allocating resources, creating eco-innovation, coordinating employee interactions, and producing green knowledge. Additionally, businesses need to learn how to efficiently manage and absorb professional environmental technologies within the enterprise, as well as how to swiftly observe the environment, comprehend the development and operation rules of the industry in which they are located, and make accurate predictions in a timely fashion (Y.

Chen, Tang, Jin, Li, & Paillé, 2015). Green dynamic capability is a high-level capability that must be progressively amassed through strategic exercises due to its robust, comprehensive, and abstract nature.

Finally, manufacturing companies should conduct themselves ethically, take on their share of social responsibility, and build a solid reputation. To further foster green dynamic capabilities and boost manufacturing businesses' competitive edge, the government should actively formulate suitable environmental regulating rules according to the size of the manufacturing enterprise, the specific industry, and the subcategory. On the other hand, there are restrictions. Factors such as survey methodologies, geographical characteristics, and level of cooperation with the questionnaires all contribute to an uneven distribution of industries, ownership types, and geographies among the sample firms. Especially for the hypothesis that is not supported, the above may influence the findings of empirical tests.

Managerial implication

In this study, the topic of environmental impact and the long-term survival of the manufacturing industry was discussed. This is a topic that continues to be an interesting area of research. In our modern era, the significance of conserving the environment and executing regulations cannot be emphasized, although the nuances involved could be tough to comprehend. This study, which was based on the resource-based view theory, shed light on the significance of corporate consciousness regarding the creation of environmentally friendly products in terms of supporting sustainability and acquiring a competitive edge. As a consequence of this, businesses are gradually beginning to recognize the need of green innovation and competitive advantage as essential strategies for effectively reaching their customers. It is essential for businesses to incorporate environmentally friendly innovation into the process of developing new product developments and production procedures. From the perspective of a number of academics, green innovation is a strategic approach that businesses adopt in order to achieve long-term success. This is accomplished by maintaining a competitive advantage while simultaneously supporting environmental sustainability. (Nwabueze & Mileski, 2018; Soewarno et al., 2019). Green marketing and environmental marketing have been implemented as corporate strategies to enhance performance growth, a crucial factor for ensuring the company's future resilience. Numerous firms must consistently engage in technology and marketing innovation in order to sustain their competitive edge (Putri & Riyanto, 2023). It will be essential to preserve a competitive edge in the present and in the future by embracing innovation and exhibiting environmental leadership when it comes to environmental issues. It is essential to do this in order to fulfill the requirements of the ever-increasing environmental rules and to fulfill the expectations of stakeholders and individual customers (Saleem et al., 2021). As a result, businesses need to reevaluate their environmental plans and implement eco-innovation strategies and sustainable competitive advantage in order to satisfy the demands of the market and complete their obligations to satisfy their corporate social responsibility (F. Shaukat et al., 2023).

This study provides significant consequences for managers of manufacturing enterprises, especially in emerging nations. The findings highlight the significance of embracing eco-innovation in order to achieve Sustainable Competitive Advantage (SCA). In order to effectively promote eco-innovation methods, managers must prioritize an environmental orientation. Hence, managers of manufacturing enterprises should include a strategic environmental orientation into their policies and business plans, with the goal of creating sustainable competitive advantage (SCA). Given the increasing environmental issues and the growing popularity of environmentally conscious consumerism, companies are confronted with substantial obstacles to their financial structures and market standings. Therefore, manufacturing firms are advised to move from a focus on adhering to regulations to a focus on outperforming competitors. By adopting sustainable practices, organizations can not only comply with regulatory criteria but also gain a long-lasting competitive edge by actively competing in the market. Policymakers should contemplate providing incentives and assistance to encourage strategic transitions in the manufacturing sector, with the aim of fostering both environmental sustainability and competitive resilience.

Limitations and Future Directions

Finally, this study has some limitations that can be considered in further studies. The study framework predominantly concentrates on manufacturing enterprises in an emerging nation. Although this offers useful insights, it restricts the extent to which the findings may be applied to a broader context. Subsequent investigations should include a range of different settings, such as service sectors, advanced economies, or additional emerging countries, in order to improve the generalizability of the research findings.

Secondly, this study mainly focuses on the analysis of eco-innovation, without exploring its different typologies. Eco-innovation can take various forms, including product innovation, process innovation, and organizational innovation. Future research would be enhanced by doing a more detailed analysis of these categories in order to reveal subtle observations and pinpoint distinct factors that contribute to each category.

Thirdly, this study primarily examines specific determinants that impact eco-innovation, such as environmental orientation, while neglecting other possible catalysts. Inter-organizational cooperation is widely recognized as a major driver of eco-innovation. Integrating supplementary elements such as collaborative dynamics, regulatory settings, or market demands could yield full comprehension of the eco-innovation ecosystem.

To overcome these constraints in future research will enhance a comprehensive and intricate comprehension of the forces influencing eco-innovation in many businesses and settings. (Pereira, MacLennan, & Tiago, 2020).

CONCLUSION

This study focused on analyzing the direct influence of green marketing orientation (GMO) with its dimensions on business performance (BP). Furthermore, the study examined how sustainable competitive advantage (SCA) and eco-innovation (EI) act as mediators

between GMO and BP. The results highlight a strong positive correlation, suggesting that the implementation of GMOs can result in a considerable rise in both SCA and EI. These improved elements, in return, have a positive impact on the overall operational effectiveness of businesses. This observation highlights the strategic significance of adopting green marketing techniques, which not only yield direct business performance gains but also promote the development of sustainable competitive advantages and the encouragement of eco-innovative behaviors within firms. This study provides empirical evidence for the NRBV which states that natural element in the corporate planning will improve organizations competitiveness.

References

- 1) Ajike, E. O., Amos, N. B., & Kabuoh, M. N. (2015). Green marketing: a tool for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Statistics, Management and Finance.*, 3, 1-14.
- 2) AlQershi, N. A., Mokhtar, S. S. M., & Abas, Z. B. (2020). CRM dimensions and performance of SMEs in Yemen: the moderating role of human capital. *Journal of Intellectual Capital.*
- 3) Aprisma, R., & Sudaryati, E. (2020). Environmental Uncertainty and Firm Performance: The Moderating Role of Corporate Governance. *Jurnal Akuntansi*, 24(2), 187-203.
- 4) Ar, I. M. (2012). The impact of green product innovation on firm performance and competitive capability: the moderating role of managerial environmental concern. *Procedia-Social Behavioral Sciences*, 62, 854-864.
- 5) Arfi, W. B., Hikkerova, L., & Sahut, J.-M. (2018). External knowledge sources, green innovation and performance. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 129, 210-220.
- 6) Armstrong, G., & Kotler, P. (2009). *Principles of Marketing: A Global Perspective*: HK: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- 7) Bakar, L. J. A., & Ahmad, H. (2010). Assessing the relationship between firm resources and product innovation performance: A resource-based view. *Business Process Management Journal.*
- 8) Banerjee, S., Bhattacharjee, B., & Kommareddy, C. (2002). *Scalable application layer multicast*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the 2002 conference on Applications, technologies, architectures, and protocols for computer communications.
- 9) Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of management*, 17(1), 99-120.
- 10) Bradley, F., & O'Reagain, S. (2001). Deriving international competitive advantage in SMEs through product-market and business system resource allocation. *Irish Journal of Management*, 22(2), 19.
- 11) Burke, M. C. (1984). Strategic choice and marketing managers: an examination of business-level marketing objectives. *Journal of marketing research*, 21(4), 345-359.
- 12) Cao, Y., Ajjan, H., Hong, P. J. A. P. J. o. M., & Logistics. (2018). Post-purchase shipping and customer service experiences in online shopping and their impact on customer satisfaction: An empirical study with comparison. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing Logistics*, 30(2), 400-416. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/APJML-04-2017-0071>
- 13) Carbonell, P., & Escudero, A. I. R. (2010). The effect of market orientation on innovation speed and new product performance. *Journal of Business Industrial Marketing*, 25 (7), 501-513. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/08858621011077736>

- 14) Chahal, H., Dangwal, R., & Raina, S. (2014). Conceptualisation, development and validation of green marketing orientation (GMO) of SMEs in India: A case of electric sector. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 5, 312-337. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-02-2014-0005>
- 15) Chang, C.-H. (2011). The influence of corporate environmental ethics on competitive advantage: The mediation role of green innovation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 104(3), 361-370.
- 16) Chang, C. H., & Chen, Y. S. J. M. D. (2013). Green organizational identity and green innovation. *Management Decision*, 51 (5), 1056–1070 doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-09-2011-0314>
- 17) Chang, N.-J., & Fong, C.-M. (2010). Green Product Quality, Green Customer Satisfaction and Green Customer Loyalty. *African Journal of Business Management*, 4.
- 18) Chatzoglou, P., & Chatzoudes, D. (2017). The role of innovation in building competitive advantages: an empirical investigation. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 21(1), 44-69.
- 19) Chen, C. (2001). Design for the environment: A quality-based model for green product development. *Management Science*, 47(2), 250-263.
- 20) Chen, J., & Liu, L. (2018). Profiting from green innovation: The moderating effect of competitive strategy. *Sustainability*, 11(1), 15.
- 21) Chen, Y.-S. (2010). The drivers of green brand equity: Green brand image, green satisfaction, and green trust. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 93(2), 307-319.
- 22) Chen, Y., Tang, G., Jin, J., Li, J., & Paillé, P. (2015). Linking market orientation and environmental performance: The influence of environmental strategy, employee's environmental involvement, and environmental product quality. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 127(2), 479-500.
- 23) Churchill Jr, G. A. (1979). A paradigm for developing better measures of marketing constructs. *Journal of marketing research*, 16(1), 64-73.
- 24) Cronin, J. J., Smith, J. S., Gleim, M. R., Ramirez, E., & Martinez, J. D. (2011). Green marketing strategies: an examination of stakeholders and the opportunities they present. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 39(1), 158-174. doi:10.1007/s11747-010-0227-0
- 25) Dabija, D.-C., Bejan, B. M., & Grant, D. B. (2018). The impact of consumer green behaviour on green loyalty among retail formats. *Moravian geographical reports*, 26(3), 173–185. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2478/mgr-2018-0014>
- 26) Dangelico, R. M., Pujari, D., & Pontrandolfo, P. (2017). Green product innovation in manufacturing firms: A sustainability-oriented dynamic capability perspective. *Business strategy and the Environment*, 26(4), 490-506.
- 27) De Marchi, V. (2012). Environmental innovation and R&D cooperation: Empirical evidence from Spanish manufacturing firms. *Research policy*, 41(3), 614-623.
- 28) Dey, P. K., Malesios, C., De, D., Budhwar, P., Chowdhury, S., & Cheffi, W. (2020). Circular economy to enhance sustainability of small and medium-sized enterprises. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 29(6), 2145-2169.
- 29) El-Kassar, A.-N., & Singh, S. K. (2019). Green innovation and organizational performance: The influence of big data and the moderating role of management commitment and HR practices. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 144, 483-498. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.12.016>
- 30) Eneizan, B., Abd Wahab, K., & Obaid, T. (2016). Effects of green marketing strategies on sales volume of green cars. *Singaporean Journal of Business, Economics Management Studies*, 51(3814), 1-14.

- 31) Eneizan, B., Abd Wahab, K., & Obaid, T. (2016). Effects of green marketing strategies on sales volume of green cars. *Singaporean Journal of Business, Economics and Management Studies*
- 32) 51(3814), 1-14.
- 33) Enzing, C. M., Batterink, M. H., Janszen, F. H., & Omta, S. O. J. B. F. J. (2011). Where innovation processes make a difference in products' short-and long-term market success. *British Food Journal*.
- 34) Falk, R. F., & Miller, N. B. (1992). *A primer for soft modeling*. Washington: University of Akron Press.
- 35) Fernández-Mesa, A., Alegre-Vidal, J., Chiva-Gómez, R., & Gutiérrez-Gracia, A. (2013). Design management capability and product innovation in SMEs. *Management Decision*.
- 36) García-Salirrosas, E. E., & Rondon-Eusebio, R. F. (2022). Green Marketing Practices Related to Key Variables of Consumer Purchasing Behavior. *Sustainability*, 14(14), 8499.
- 37) Gbadeyan, R. A. O., & Omolekan, O. J. (2015). Relevance of green marketing on environmental degradation: an empirical study of consumers of green products in Benin City. *University of Mauritius Research Journal*, 21, 1-25.
- 38) Han, S.-R., Li, P., Xiang, J.-J., Luo, X.-H., Chen, C.-Y. J. E. S., & Research, P. (2020). Does the institutional environment influence corporate social responsibility? Consideration of green investment of enterprises—evidence from China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 1-18.
- 39) Hart, O. (1995). *Firms, contracts, and financial structure*. New York: Clarendon press.
- 40) Hart, S. L., & Dowell, G. (2011). Invited editorial: A natural-resource-based view of the firm: Fifteen years after. *Journal of management*, 37(5), 1464-1479.
- 41) Ionescu, L. (2020). The Economics of the Carbon Tax. *Geopolitics, History, International Relations*, 12(1), 101-107.
- 42) Iqbal, A., Kazmi, S. Q., Anwar, A., Ramish, M. S., & Salam, A. (2023). Impact Of Green Marketing On Green Purchase Intention And Green Consumption Behavior: The Moderating Role Of Green Concern. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 975-993.
- 43) Jämsä, P., Tähtinen, J., Ryan, A., Pallari, M. J. J. o. S. B., & Development, E. (2011). Sustainable SMEs network utilization: the case of food enterprises. *Journal of Small Business Enterprise Development*, 18(1), 141–156. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/14626001111106479>
- 44) Kautish, P., & Sharma, R. (2020). Determinants of pro-environmental behavior and environmentally conscious consumer behavior: An empirical investigation from emerging market. *Business Strategy and Development*, 3(1), 112-127.
- 45) Kilbourne, W. E., Beckmann, S. C., & Thelen, E. (2002). The role of the dominant social paradigm in environmental attitudes: a multinational examination. *Journal of Business Research*, 55(3), 193-204. doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963\(00\)00141-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0148-2963(00)00141-7)
- 46) Kohli, A. K., & Jaworski, B. (1990). Market orientation: the construct, research propositions, and managerial implications. *Journal of marketing*, 54(2), 1-18.
- 47) Kong, D., Feng, Q., Zhou, Y., & Xue, L. (2016). Local implementation for green-manufacturing technology diffusion policy in China: from the user firms' perspectives. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 129, 113-124.
- 48) Kotler, P. (2011). Reinventing marketing to manage the environmental imperative. *Journal of marketing*, 75(4), 132-135.
- 49) Kotler, P., Armstrong, G., Ang, S. H., Leong, S. M., Tan, C. T., & YAU, O. (2008). Principles of marketing: An global perspective.

- 50) Kumar, P., & Ghodeswar, B. M. (2015). Factors affecting consumers' green product purchase decisions. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 33(3), 330-347. doi:10.1108/MIP-03-2014-0068
- 51) Kusi-Sarpong, S., Bai, C., Sarkis, J., & Wang, X. (2015). Green supply chain practices evaluation in the mining industry using a joint rough sets and fuzzy TOPSIS methodology. *Resources Policy*, 46, 86-100. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resourpol.2014.10.011
- 52) Latan, H., Jabbour, C. J. C., de Sousa Jabbour, A. B. L., Wamba, S. F., & Shahbaz, M. (2018). Effects of environmental strategy, environmental uncertainty and top management's commitment on corporate environmental performance: The role of environmental management accounting. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 180, 297-306.
- 53) Lavrinenko, O., Ignatjeva, S., Ohotina, A., Rybalkin, O., & Lazdans, D. (2019). The role of green economy in sustainable development (case study: the EU states). *Entrepreneurship and sustainability Issues*, 6, 1113-1126.
- 54) Ledwith, A., & O'Dwyer, M. (2008). Product launch, product advantage and market orientation in SMEs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*.
- 55) Leonidou, C. N., Katsikeas, C. S., & Morgan, N. A. (2013). "Greening" the marketing mix: Do firms do it and does it pay off? *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 41(2), 151-170.
- 56) Lertpachin, C., Wingwon, B., & Noithonglek, T. (2013). The effect of marketing focus, innovation and learning organization on the building of competitive advantages: empirical evidence from ISO 9000 certified companies. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 21(4), 323-331.
- 57) Lin, R.-J., Chen, R.-H., & Huang, F.-H. (2014). Green innovation in the automobile industry. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 114(6), 886-903. doi:10.1108/IMDS-11-2013-0482
- 58) Lin, R.-J., Tan, K.-H., & Geng, Y. (2013). Market demand, green product innovation, and firm performance: evidence from Vietnam motorcycle industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 40, 101-107.
- 59) Liu, X., Yang, J., Qu, S., Wang, L., Shishime, T., & Bao, C. (2012). Sustainable production: practices and determinant factors of green supply chain management of Chinese companies. *Business strategy and the Environment*, 21(1), 1-16.
- 60) Maçaneiro, M. B., da Cunha, S. K., & Balbinot, Z. (2013). Drivers of the adoption of eco-innovations in the pulp, paper, and paper products industry in Brazil. *Latin American Business Review*, 14(3-4), 179-208.
- 61) Mady, K., Abdul Halim, M. A. S., & Omar, K. (2022). Drivers of multiple eco-innovation and the impact on sustainable competitive advantage: evidence from manufacturing SMEs in Egypt. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 14(1), 40-61.
- 62) Mahdi, O. R., & Almsafir, M. K. (2014). The role of strategic leadership in building sustainable competitive advantage in the academic environment. *Procedia-Social Behavioral Sciences*, 129, 289-296.
- 63) Mannan, B., Khurana, S., & Haleem, A. (2016). Modeling of critical factors for integrating sustainability with innovation for Indian small-and medium-scale manufacturing enterprises: An ISM and MICMAC approach. *Cogent Business Management*, 3(1), 1140318.
- 64) Martínez, P. (2015). Customer loyalty: Exploring its antecedents from a green marketing perspective. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 25(5), 896-917. doi:https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-03-2014-0115

- 65) May, A. Y. C., Hao, G. S., & Carter, S. (2021). Intertwining corporate social responsibility, employee green behavior, and environmental sustainability: the mediation effect of organizational trust and organizational identity. *Economics, Management Financial Markets*, 16(2), 32-61.
- 66) Meirun, T., Makhloufi, L., & Ghazali Hassan, M. (2020). Environmental outcomes of green entrepreneurship harmonization. *Sustainability*, 12(24), 10615.
- 67) Moravcikova, D., Krizanova, A., Kliestikova, J., & Rypakova, M. (2017). Green Marketing as the Source of the Competitive Advantage of the Business. *Sustainability*, 9(12), 2218.
- 68) Mukonza, C., & Swarts, I. (2020). The influence of green marketing strategies on business performance and corporate image in the retail sector. *Business strategy and the Environment*, 29(3), 838-845.
- 69) Nandakumar, M., Ghobadian, A., & O'Regan, N. (2010). Business-level strategy and performance: The moderating effects of environment and structure. *Management Decision*.
- 70) Nuryakin, N., & Maryati, T. (2020). Green product competitiveness and green product success. Why and how does mediating affect green innovation performance? *Entrepreneurship and sustainability Issues*, 7(4), 3061.
- 71) Nuryakin, N., & Maryati, T. (2022). Do green innovation and green competitive advantage mediate the effect of green marketing orientation on SMEs' green marketing performance? *Cogent Business & Management*, 9(1), 2065948. doi:10.1080/23311975.2022.2065948
- 72) Nwabueze, U., & Mileski, J. (2018). Achieving competitive advantage through effective communication in a global environment. *Journal of International Studies*, 11(1).
- 73) Papadas, K.-K., Avlonitis, G. J., & Carrigan, M. (2017). Green marketing orientation: Conceptualization, scale development and validation. *Journal of Business Research*, 80, 236-246.
- 74) Papadas, K.-K., Avlonitis, G. J., Carrigan, M., & Piha, L. (2019). The interplay of strategic and internal green marketing orientation on competitive advantage. *Journal of Business Research*, 104, 632-643.
- 75) Peattie, K., & Crane, A. (2005). Green marketing: legend, myth, farce or prophesy? *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 8(4), 357-370. doi:10.1108/13522750510619733
- 76) Pereira, R. M., MacLennan, M. L. F., & Tiago, E. F. (2020). Interorganizational cooperation and eco-innovation: a literature review. *International Journal of Innovation Science*, 12(5), 477-493.
- 77) Porter, M. E. (1989). From competitive advantage to corporate. *Readings in Strategic Management*, 234.
- 78) Pujari, D., Wright, G., & Peattie, K. (2003). Green and competitive: Influences on environmental new product development performance. *Journal of Business Research*, 56(8), 657-671.
- 79) Putri, V. P., & Riyanto, D. W. U. (2023). GREEN INNOVATION AND GREEN COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE MEDIATE THE INFLUENCE OF GREEN MARKETING ORIENTATION ON GREEN MARKETING PERFORMANCE IN SME INDONESIA. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research*, 7(4).
- 80) Qi, G., Zou, H., & Xie, X. (2020). Governmental inspection and green innovation: Examining the role of environmental capability and institutional development. *Corporate Social Responsibility Environmental Management*, 27(4), 1774-1785.
- 81) Ringle, C. M., Wende, S., & Will, A. (2005). SmartPLS 2.0 (M3) Beta. In. Hamburg, Germany: University of Hamburg.
- 82) Rivera, J., & Clement, V. (2019). Business adaptation to climate change: American ski resorts and warmer temperatures. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(7), 1285-1301.

- 83) Salavou, H., & Avlonitis, G. (2008). Product innovativeness and performance: a focus on SMEs. *Management Decision*, 46(7), 969-985.
- 84) Saleem, F., Zhang-Zhang, Y., Gopinath, C., & Malik, M. I. (2021). Antecedents of environmental strategies: a study of the manufacturing industry in Pakistan. *International Journal of Emerging Markets*.
- 85) Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Henseler, J., & Hair, J. F. (2014). On the emancipation of PLS-SEM: A commentary on Rigdon (2012). *Long Range Planning*, 47(3), 154-160.
- 86) Sezen, B., & Cankaya, S. Y. (2013). Effects of green manufacturing and eco-innovation on sustainability performance. *Procedia-Social Behavioral Sciences*, 99, 154-163.
- 87) Shahzad, M., Qu, Y., Javed, S. A., Zafar, A. U., & Rehman, S. U. (2020). Relation of environment sustainability to CSR and green innovation: A case of Pakistani manufacturing industry. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 253, 119938. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119938
- 88) Sharma, A. P. (2021). Consumers' purchase behaviour and green marketing: A synthesis, review and agenda. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 45(6), 1217-1238.
- 89) Shaukat, F., Zaman, H., Nguyen, T., & Souvanhxay, P. (2023). The Interplay of Eco-Innovation and Market Uncertainty on Green Marketing Orientation and Business Performance.
- 90) Shaukat, S., Nawaz, M. S., & Naz, S. (2013). Effects of innovation types on firm performance: An empirical study on Pakistan's manufacturing sector. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce Social Sciences*, 7(2), 243-262.
- 91) Simão, L., & Lisboa, A. (2017). Green marketing and green brand—The Toyota Case. *Procedia manufacturing*, 12, 183-194.
- 92) Simpson, M. (2004). Competitive Advantage in SMEs: Organising for Innovation and Change. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*.
- 93) Slater, S. F., & Narver, J. C. (1995). Market orientation and the learning organization. *Journal of marketing*, 59(3), 63-74.
- 94) Soebandrija, K. E. N. (2017). *Green innovation and sustainable industrial systems within sustainability and company improvement perspective*. Paper presented at the IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science.
- 95) Soewarno, N., Tjahjadi, B., & Fithrianti, F. (2019). Green innovation strategy and green innovation: The roles of green organizational identity and environmental organizational legitimacy. *Management Decision*, 57(11), 3061-3078.
- 96) Soewarno, N., Tjahjadi, B., & Permatanadia, D. (2020). Competitive pressure and business performance in East Java Batik industry. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics Business*, 7(12), 329-336.
- 97) Suler, P., Palmer, L., & Bilan, S. (2021). Internet of Things sensing networks, digitized mass production, and sustainable organizational performance in cyber-physical system-based smart factories. *Journal of Self-Governance and Management Economics*, 9(2), 42-51.
- 98) Teece, D. J. (2018). Business models and dynamic capabilities. *Long range planning*, 51(1), 40-49.
- 99) Wang, C.-H. (2019). How organizational green culture influences green performance and competitive advantage: The mediating role of green innovation. *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30. doi:10.1108/JMTM-09-2018-0314

- 100) Wanjohi, P., Gachoka, H., Kihoro, J., & Ogutu, M. (2013). Green business: potential for application as a business innovation for wealth and employment creation in Kenya. *Global Business and Economics Research Journal*, 2(9), 1-12.
- 101) Wells, V. K., Manika, D., Gregory-Smith, D., Taheri, B., & McCowlen, C. (2015). Heritage tourism, CSR and the role of employee environmental behaviour. *Tourism Management*, 48, 399-413.
- 102) Wong, S. K. S. (2012). The influence of green product competitiveness on the success of green product innovation: Empirical evidence from the Chinese electrical and electronics industry. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 15, 468-490. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1108/14601061211272385>
- 103) Zhang, L., Xue, L., & Zhou, Y. (2019). How do low-carbon policies promote green diffusion among alliance-based firms in China? An evolutionary-game model of complex networks. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 210, 518-529.
- 104) Zhou, S. S., Zhou, A. J., Feng, J., Jiang, S. J. J. o. M., & Organization. (2019). Dynamic capabilities and organizational performance: The mediating role of innovation. *Journal of Management Organization*, 25(5), 731-747.
- 105) Zhou, Y., Hong, J., Zhu, K., Yang, Y., & Zhao, D. J. J. o. C. P. (2018). Dynamic capability matters: uncovering its fundamental role in decision making of environmental innovation. 177, 516-526.
- 106) Zhu, Q., & Sarkis, J. (2004). Relationships between operational practices and performance among early adopters of green supply chain management practices in Chinese manufacturing enterprises. *Journal of Operations Management*, 22(3), 265-289.